

TITLE: PERFORMANCE OF MODELING AND SIMULATION IN ANALYZING BUSINESS SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT:

To view business as a system allows us to analyze its reactions and outcomes, modelling and simulation tools can ease the complex procedures of system analysis and develop them in a beneficial way. This study observed the power of simulation to detect, differentiate, measure, and optimize variables, it reviewed the most relevant papers and monitored different indexes which are vital to the system and found how far simulation has been capable of analyzing the process and measuring the change or improvement subject to the present constraints. Based on reviews and the obtained results, simulation tools can be used to improve current performance of systems by optimizing crucial parameters such as profit, cost, time cycle, utilization, which leads to avoiding loss, damage, rework, overwork, inefficient maintenance, extra transportation and increasing profitability and popularity of the business, at the other hand it can also be used as a predictive and preventive tool to test creative ideas ahead of their live implementation that saves the business before undergoing wrong strategies and warns investors ahead of investing in wrong projects and beginning to flow capital into startups with underperformance or unacceptable rate of return.

Keywords: Optimization, Rate of Change, Predictability, Failure Prevention

INTRODUCTION

Modelling and Simulation is a very convenient tool to carry out complex data structure and can analyze different systems including businesses, but they have not been introduced clearly to people and raising awareness about their role in easing analysis tasks and improving system performance is what this paper is working on. "In the context of management training business simulation games are increasingly emerging as pedagogical tools for motivating and engaging players actively in the learning experience". (Bitrián, P., Buil, I., & Catalán, S., 2020) In the age of data and information, knowledge of applying data to produce desirable output is a must and it can help companies and governments enhance their output to be more productive, more efficient, more economically beneficial and less depreciated, one of the key tools to do such task is modelling, simulation and optimization.

Beside the beneficial advantages of simulation, it can also act as a preventive tool to avoid implementing business ideas which will lead to failure or loss in the short term or long term. "Automation of manufacturing processes, commonly recognized as a pro-efficiency solution, is not always a beneficial solution for the organization. There are cases when automation becomes a costly trap, having a negative impact on the broadly understood efficiency of processes, quality and operating costs. The need to reduce the risk associated with automation forces companies to look for solutions to identify potential threats and reduce their negative impact on the organization's results. One of such solutions may be a computer simulation, which with its tools can support strategic business decisions". (Jarosław Maćków, 2023).

In general, sensitivity and reaction quality of simulation tools should be sufficient to detect a failure or to measure amount of loss or profit or in other words to clearly analyze the system, otherwise the results will carry errors and misguide which can be a big problem particularly if the tested idea be implemented in real life, in some fields like surgery, medical and medicine this error can have a huge impact and in fields like business it can lead to financial or safety failure and in fields like education it can misguide a generation therefore it is necessary for simulation techniques to be intelligent enough in detecting the defective or in measuring the loss, profit and other variables. "Business process simulation is a versatile technique to predict the impact of one or more changes on the performance of a process. Process simulation is often used to identify sets of changes that optimize one or more performance measures". (López-Pintado, O., Dumas, M., 2024)

Objective of the Study

Since the stated problem in the study is lack of awareness about the power of modeling, simulation as an applicable tool to analyze systems, therefore the objective of this study is to determine the power of modeling and simulation techniques to differentiate and to measure the change and to open space for testing different feasible ideas which result in increase of positive factors and reduction of negative factors, including various factors such as cycle time, productivity, temperature, energy, cost, profit and many others which can change the final output of a system and since these factors are of different units and diverse nature, the study will offer a formula to standardize them for proper comparison and analysis.

METHODS

The first step was to review different papers relevant to modelling, simulation and business in order to extract information, data and knowledge to become able to analyze what is found in those papers, the second step was to search for 4 main keywords: 1-Business 2-Modelling 3-Simulation 4-System in platform such as ScienceDirect, IEEE and to pick up the most relevant content and data., the third step was to filter the obtained data in the most appropriate way therefor the number of 205 research papers were selected in the beginning and after title check and content review 129 of them got eliminated due to irrelevance to the details of this research and 42 were not used due to incompatibility or inaccessibility of relevant data, one research was also removed because of qualitative comparison and lack of enough numerical input. At the end, 33 research papers were chosen for data collection (Figure 1), analysis and citation and all of them were published within 2014-2024(year). So simply, reviewing 205 papers, filtering 129, focusing on 33 and considering research papers from the years 2014 to 2024. The available data for a single business or industry was quite limited so it used data coming from different business systems with different outcome scales.

Figure 1

Research Gap

Majority of papers have focused on applying modeling and simulation technique into a specific business to improve the results or to predict the results of implementing a new idea in that business, at the other side some researchers have also studied about application of simulation to boost

educational indices and to improve students' performance, however this research didn't find sufficient papers which have concentrated on power of modeling, simulation tools and their sensitivity to measure change and differentiation regardless of the nature of business. Therefor to acquire a general vision, it looked at various types of businesses and monitored how simulation techniques could be applicable to measure change in these businesses independent of their nature, location and size.

Data Collection and Interpretation

After selecting the most relevant content, the study searched for a section in papers where data were available for measuring and analysis, different indices and metrics were eligible to be studied as long as it could show the capability of the simulation technique used in that research to measure the difference, improvement, sensitivity or change which represent the power and precision of simulation technique. The diversity and variety of these data presents different numbers in different scales, for example number of small products in microscopic scale are huge, but number of big mines in a city are limited and relatively small, to be able to compare numbers with various scales and standardize them, all the differences were measured by percentage because it can be a standard format for comparison.

The following example may clarify how data were interpreted for analyzing:

Business 1 Old:

Productivity Ratio: 5 Cycle Time: 85 Seconds
Utilization Rate: 45%

Business 2 Old:

Costs: 1000000 Profit: 50000

Transportation time: 3.42 hours

If the two companies apply some ideas to improve the mentioned factors and they use modelling, simulation to evaluate the proposed system design compared to the old one, the exemplified systems new results would be:

Business 1 New:

Productivity Ratio: 6 Cycle Time: 67secs

Utilization Rate: 47%

Business 2 New:

Costs: 950000USD Profit: 65000USD

Transportation time: 2.9 hours

System 1	Old	New
Productivity	5	6
Cycle Time	85	67
Utilization Rate	45	39

Table1. System1 current and proposed statuses

System 2	Old	New
Cost	1000000	950000
Profit	50000	65000
Transportation Time	3.42	2.9

Table2. System2 current and proposed statuses

The nature of the two example businesses is assumed to be different and their essential factors are also different, and it is observed that units of those factors are quite different too, so the numbers representing the change in their systems also seem unlike as follows:

$$\text{Diff11(Productivity)} = 1 \quad \text{Diff12(Cycle Time)} = -18$$

$$\text{Diff13(Utilization)} = -6$$

$$\text{Diff21(Cost)} = -50000 \quad \text{Diff22(Profit)} = 15000$$

$$\text{Diff23(Transportation Time)} = -0.52$$

However, to reach a standard and put all these numbers under one category to determine the ability of modelling, simulation to measure the change, the IDiff% index was introduced to be used with the following formula.

$$\text{Diff} = V2 - V1$$

$$D = \text{ABS}((\text{MAX}(V1, V2) - \text{MIN}(V1, V2)))$$

$$\text{I-Diff}\% = (D / \text{MAX}(\text{ABS}(V1), \text{ABS}(V2))) * 100$$

Where V1 represents values in the old system and V2 represents values in the new or proposed system.

System 1	Diff	I-Diff %
Productivity	1	16.66
Cycle Time	-18	21.17
Utilization Rate	-6	13.33

Table3. System1 Change Determination

System 2	Diff	I-Diff %
Cost	-50000	5
Profit	15000	23.07
Transportation Time	-0.52	15.2

Table4. System2 Change Determination

Now these results can come into one category as percentage numbers and further be used as data to represent the percentage of change in system to evaluate the power of modeling and simulation to measure the change in various business systems.

In the next step a table of differentiation percentages were provided upon calculating all the available numbers associated with [figure 2](#), the average of those numbers was calculated to determine the capability of modelling and simulation in changing business-related systems. Since

most of reviewed papers were meant to improve the system by optimizing different variables, therefore this change can also represent the power of modelling and simulation to change or improve the current situation to some degree, the higher this change is the more simulation can be applicable for business systems.

Figure 2

RESULTS

Upon data collection and analysis, the output results implies that modelling, simulation can measure and detect the change in process outcomes by 36 percent in average (Table 5), although the size of change could be different in various businesses, but the change is usually an apparent result of simulation studies because by reviewing the current system the researcher tends to figure out the lacks and flaws of the system and accordingly generate ideas to improve the system, moreover by using simulation they can even anticipate the results of those improvements.

VAR: Variance

SD: Standard Deviation

CV: Coefficient of Variation

MEAN	VAR	SD	CV
36.95302	9.355948	3.058749	8.277399

Table 5

The computed percentage as result of data analysis is a relatively reasonable and satisfying percent that highlights the effect of modelling, simulation techniques in changing

business systems to become quite better, in other words more productive, more efficient, more profitable, safer and more predictable and at the other hand less costly and less time consuming. The variance and coefficient of variation of available data also implies that the change is somehow sustainable for diverse types of businesses meaning that simulation can be applicable for a wide range of business systems.

DISCUSSION

The reasonable percentage of change (36.95302) detected by simulation tool implies the applicability of modelling and simulation techniques to make remarkable change in process outcomes, therefore this skill should be applied in more businesses to enhance the system and increase the profit aside minimizing errors and failures. Fast response of modern simulation tools can help implement innovative ideas without undergoing the maximum risk of failure, because simulation ahead of time warns us about risky and unstable results of probable outcomes. One of the aptitudes of innovative and fast-growing businesses is their speed to adopt technology and change and consequently react in the most optimum way to survive the market and simulation can be one of the powerful techniques to be applied for this purpose. However future research is required to study and cover the lacks and flaws of modelling, simulation in each phase of analysis to minimize the error and guide the company to desired results. Note that modeling consists of defining objectives and constraints is a vital phase that comes before simulation, system must be compatible and adoptable with the new proposed change, otherwise although simulation shows ideal results, but if the proposed idea is not feasible within the boundaries of constraints and if constraints are not well validated during modelling, implementation and execution of that idea will lead to lose and failure, so it is critical and prior to do the modeling step properly before applying simulation results and implementation of ideas.

Scope and Limitation

This paper is bounded to the field of modelling and simulation at one side and the field of business at the other side, but the research can further be expanded to scientific experiences, engineering projects and many other fields from industry to education. Moreover, it focuses only on recent 10 years research data which could be more relevant to the current age, it also has not distinguished how simulation can affect specific factors such as cycle time or cost, but it has generally studied how intelligent and sensitive can modelling and simulation work in measuring the change rate among those factors. It emphasizes the ability of modeling and simulation as a technique to improve various types of business systems generally, regardless of their nature, so it does not go deeply through specific types of businesses and study them one by one.

Recommendation

Businesses and similarly analyzable systems should begin to apply system modelling and simulation to welcome and test creative ideas in a simulated approach without encountering unpleasant experiences, elementary losses and unnecessary waste. One way to do this is to educate modeling and simulation to the future generations and boost their abilities to design, analyze and improve systems in logical, mathematical and scientific ways.

Future Research

Future researchers who are interested in modeling, simulation and optimization of systems can further dedicate their time and resources to increase awareness about the role of simulation techniques to develop and improve society. Future researchers can work on many aspects of modeling and simulation such as the followings:

- Development of simulation tools
- Development of modeling tools
- Discovering modelling, simulation cons and pros in a specific industry
- Increase dimensions of simulation study to reach more accurate results.
- Prediction of the results of long-term projects (from construction projects to moon landing projects)
- Educational aspects of modelling, simulation and optimization

CONCLUSION

In the age of information and data, companies have realized the importance of collecting, applying and analyzing data to produce desirable results. This study also determined that the power of simulation to differentiate and measure the change is reasonable or briefly it's an appropriate technique to analyze data and systems, and according to results it can still be applied in wider range of systems to achieve goals in an optimum way. Future research can expand the knowledge in more aspects of modeling and simulation because it has shown promising results and there are still many remained parts of the puzzle to be studied about simulation since it is a useful tool, but has not been applied by substantial number of businesses.

Data Availability

Data and details are available upon request to the email address of the author.

The following references include reviewed papers which data and content were imported from and implemented in this study, and does not include irrelevant, incompatible and other unrelated reviewed papers.

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